

(Assessment of Career Aspiration on Academic Performance among Secondary School Biology ... Junaidu, #. 1. 2025)

Assessment of Career Aspiration on Academic Performance among Secondary School Biology Students in Sabon Gari Local Government Area, Kaduna State, Nigeria

JUNAIDU, Hafsah Ishaq
hafsahjunaid@yahoo.com
08069237954

Samaru College of Agriculture, Division of Agricultural Colleges, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria.

Abstract

This study Assessment of Career aspiration on academic performance among secondary school Biology Students in Sabon gari Local Government Area, Kaduna State, Nigeria. The study employed the descriptive research design method which was guided by two research questions and two research hypotheses. The sample for the study was 260 respondents which consisted of senior secondary school II students' during the 2024/2025 academic session which were randomly selected from 15 public secondary schools within Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Zaria Educational Zone. Data were obtained using Career Aspiration of Biology Students Questionnaire (CABSQ) with a reliability coefficient of 0.92 and the inferential statistics (t-test) was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The result revealed that there was no significant difference between career preferences and career aspirations among Biology students in Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State; Based on the findings, it was recommended that senior secondary school students should be encouraged from time to time to visit the counseling unit whenever the need arises, students should be acquainted with this services so that they can be properly guided on their academics and career aspirations and preferences; and that career professionals such as teachers and counsellors should attend workshops, seminars that will help broaden their skills and knowledge in the field of Biology and its related disciplines.

Keywords: *(Career, Career Aspirations, Career Preference, Academic Performance)*

Introduction

Biology is one of the subjects that form an essential component in the sciences and technology area. Other important subjects are chemistry, physics and mathematics, the knowledge of biology helps students to join in the vast oriented biological career like medicine agriculture, food industries, zoology and environmental management. DeBoer (2019) reported that it was until the growth of academy in the late 1700's that science was brought to the secondary education, and since then the study of Biology has become a basic foundation of career aspirations in many related fields. The contribution of biology to human life and its relevance to various developmental programs justifies its inclusion as a compulsory subject at the O-level of secondary education and within the prescribed combinations at the A-level (Aileni, 2022). Biology provides foundational knowledge crucial for understanding health, agriculture, environmental sustainability, and biotechnology, which are all vital sectors in the advancement of human society (Shiyo, 2023).

(Assessment of Career Aspiration on Academic Performance among Secondary School Biology ... Junaidu, H. I. 2025)

In the 21st century, the ability to create and apply innovative knowledge and skills has become essential for individuals and nations to thrive in the global economy. This underscores the importance of equipping students with biological literacy to enable them to contribute meaningfully to wealth creation and national development (Olofin et al., 2023). Therefore, a sound understanding of biology not only empowers students to make informed decisions about their health and environment but also prepares them to engage effectively in the world of work, where scientific knowledge is increasingly valued (Brahma, 2025). Msanbwa et al., (2024) identified some of the factors contributing to poor performance in sciences which include: lack of self-confidence, interest, negative attitudes, and perceptions from which students are motivated to gain knowledge and master skills which provides the link with the occupations in world of work. Subasman and Aliyyah (2023) agree that career aspiration as the process of individuals in setting of career goals which enables them to make realistic choices in the world of work.

The study of Biology subject provides a large number of areas in which biology class may have been the choices for further career paths leading to the choice of specific job to perform in their entire life. Zhang (2023) contend that biology provide students with information about knowledge, skills and values which enable them to identify different career related to biology, their potentials and to manage tasks and help them to make decision before choosing the career. On the other hand, to provide the nation with reliable information on the overall trend in the preferences in scientific occupation, to provide sound basis on the nature of responses and advancement in science and technology, also on how to adjust the science curricula so that it can meet preparation of the manpower to suit a constantly changing societies in the world (Zhang, 2023).

In a formal way, students aspiring for the occupations in which they are performing well in subjects' continuous assessment. According to Eccles and Wigfield (2024) if students are doing well in biology tests, examinations and practical works it is expected that they will do well in the future on those career paths and later in the related occupations. Eccles and Wigfield (2024) further viewed that, these predications elicit choices in biological occupations and vice versa for those who are performing less as the evidence of students possessing the qualities fits the career. Iftikhar (2024) posited that, in this case, students who are not performing well in biology may be discouraged to choose the related career, while others may unconsciously choose. This leads the students to end up in choosing wrong career which do not match with their abilities, interest, and values and remain in confusion therefore, in the situation where importance of human resource, particularly biological careers development increases every day, promotion, specification and expression of occupations is very crucial to meet the national aspirations (McDonald & Hite, 2023).

Ramly, Ismail and Juli (2009) define career as a "chosen pursuit that called profession". In general, it consist of all the changes in values, attitude and motivation that occur as a person

www.zystemfugusau.com.ng
des@fugusau.edu.ng

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15674301>

(Assessment of Career Aspiration on Academic Performance among Secondary School Biology ... Junaidu, #. 1. 2025)

grows older. It describes one's working life towards professional achievement, or is taken as a course of successive situation that makes up a person's work life. Career is believed to offer structure: it also directs and provides meaningful purpose to the individuals' daily activities. It provides an idea of planning and structuring career development for example, In Biology students can be encouraged to explore the alternative professions in which one can engage. (Quinlan & Renninger, 2022). Addressing the importance of career aspirations to the human life, Gutman and Akerman says: "the greater failure is not the child who does not reach the star, but the child who has no star that they feel they are reaching for (Gutman and Ackerman, 2008)".

Difference activities performed by biologist, play a major role of exposing biological careers to students in various areas of life. In Nigeria careers in biology are found in many spheres of life. Students prepare for a career in one of a dozen specialties in Biology, microbiology and physiology student can also be trained to teach biology in secondary schools and colleges work in laboratories. In the wildlife sectors, agriculture as well as in the marine, dental, veterinary, medicinal fields or pharmacy, or for other professional training in the programmes relates to the environments, just to mention but a few. The areas of work in which biology is applied may help the students to look for options in the subjects on the prospective career and appreciate the subject better, which in turn influences the students choice of career and this may directly or indirectly affect their performance (Quinlan & Renninger, 2022).

Fowler et al., (2024) contend that careers in biology are geared towards the use of biology principles and methods to solve problems. The various fields/ areas /subject topics which were being taught in the syllabi from which could encourage students to prepare a biology related career (McCartney & Colon, 2023). The topic /subtopics were as follows: plant, pollution, depletion of our natural resources, drugs and food security, viruses, bacterial, chemical warfare, genetic engineering, over population, birth control, abortion and ideas of inheritance. Since many works involve working in the interesting location in the world, this could encourage students to prefer different careers in Biology (Drymiotou et al., 2021). Career choice, abilities and interests as reflected by achievement or aspiration indicator, therefore, directly or indirectly influence preference and performance. On the other hand, the study made by Roney and Soicher (2022) showed that the consequences of career success or failure are linked with an individual's self-concept, identity and satisfaction with career and life. According to Ghaleb (2024) a deliberate attempt by an individual to become more aware of his/her own skills, interest, value, opportunities constrains and choices was found important too. Ghaleb (2024) contends that the mutual relationship between the aspirations of parents for their children and those of the children themselves in career choices influence their academic performance and later decision making in choices of careers. However, students who are more gifted academically and believe that they can achieve success tend to have higher aspiration towards science careers (Ngezi, 2005). Therefore, this study investigated career aspirations among biology students in senior secondary schools in Sabon Gari LGA, Kaduna state, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The study of Biology with an understanding of its prospective careers is essential for students in secondary schools. It enables them to apply the knowledge and information gained to aspire for different occupations in their life time. In most cases, many students face challenges in planning for their future career which matches with their studied subjects. Many factors are responsible to this. A problem of not knowing exactly how to achieve goals at the end of education cycle, to fulfil aspirations, is serious among Sabon Gari Secondary Schools Students. The unfulfilled expectations at the end of academic education are among the reasons for many secondary School Students career choices mistake. This might be due to their low knowledge of their career aspirations. It is conceivable that, biology sciences, not only set a break to individual learner, but also, deprives the nation of future scientists' resources. As a result, the ability of an individual, as well as that of the nation to excel scientifically, technologically, and economically is hindered. This study, therefore, examined students' career aspirations in Biology.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to find out the relationship between biology study and career aspirations. To realize this purpose, the study specifically sought to:

- 1.Examine career preferences of Biology students in Sabon Gari Local Government Area, Kaduna state, Nigeria.
- 2.Find out the various sources of career information available to Biology students' in Sabon Gari Local Government Area, Kaduna state, Nigeria.

Research Questions

In order to make this work meaningful, attempts were made to answer the following questions:

1. What are the career preferences of Biology students in Sabon Gari Local Government Area, Kaduna state, Nigeria?
2. What are the sources of career information available to Biology students in Sabon Gari Local Government Area, Kaduna state, Nigeria?

Null Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

Ho₁: There is no significant difference between career preferences and career aspirations among biology students in Sabon Gari Local Government Area, Kaduna state.

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship difference between career aspirations and academic performance among biology students in Sabon Gari Local Government Area, Kaduna state.

Methodology

The study examines career aspirations of biology students in secondary schools within Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State. The nature of the study is quantitative, hence a descriptive research design that was comparative in nature was used in this study. The design

(Assessment of Career Aspiration on Academic Performance among Secondary School Biology ... Junaidu, #. 1. 2025)

was seen as suitable in this study because it examined the state of the phenomenon as it exists at the time of the study. The population of this study consists of all the nine hundred and thirty-four (934) male and female public senior secondary school two (SSS II) students in the eleven (11) senior secondary schools within Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Zaria education zone, Kaduna State. The rationale for choosing senior secondary school II (SSS II) students is that they are offering the subject biology and should be able to give the required information for the study. Purposive sampling technique was employed to select two hundred and sixty (260) respondents at random from the eleven (11) public senior secondary schools within Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Zaria Educational Zone, Kaduna State.

Data were obtained through the administration of Career Aspiration of Biology Students Questionnaire (CABSQ) which was subjected to face and content validation by three experts: one from the Department of Educational Foundations and Curriculum, one from the Department of Science Education and one from the Department of Educational Psychology and Counselling, all in Faculty of Education, Ahmadu Bello University Zaria. These experts scrutinized the instrument in terms of: clarity of instruction to the subject, proper wording of the items, appropriateness and adequacy of the items for the study, structure and adequate timing. The input from these experts was used to modify the questionnaire items.

In order to determine and establish the reliability of the instrument. The test-retest reliability method was employed in this study. The instrument was administered twice to the sampled respondent, after two weeks interval. This was to measure the degree of consistency or stability overtime. To determine the reliability coefficient of the instrument. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to calculate the r-value. A Reliability Coefficient of 0.92 was obtained. This indicated that the instrument is reliable.

Data were collected through the administered questionnaires. The distribution of the questionnaire was personally done in the sampled senior secondary schools by the researcher. Copies of the questionnaire were administered to the respondents and was collected immediately after it was completed. This ensured higher return rate. Secondly, the researcher responded to the respondents' questions in cases of difficulties. All copies of the questionnaire distributed to the students were collected at the spot after responding to them. The data obtained were analyzed using frequency distributions and simple percentages to answer the research questions. Considerable use of tables for presentation and analysis of the data were made. The Inferential statistics (Paired sample t-test) was used to test the null hypotheses at $p < 0.05$ level of significance.

Presentation of Results

Research Question One: What are the career preferences of Biology students in Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State? The data generated were analyzed and used to draw Table 1.1

Table 1: Biology Students Career Choice in Order of Preference

www.zijstemfugusau.com.ng
 des@fugusau.edu.ng

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15674301>

(Assessment of Career Aspiration on Academic Performance among Secondary School Biology ... Junaidu, #. 1. 2025)

Career Preference	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Medicine and Surgery	51	19.62
Nursing Science	22	08.46
Veterinary Medicine	13	05.00
Microbiology	46	17.69
Laboratory Science	14	05.38
Biological Science	17	06.54
Agricultural Science	11	04.23
Computer Science	42	16.15
Pharmacy	23	08.85
Lecturer/Teacher	21	08.08
Total	260	100

Data presented in Table 1 reveal that most of the students 51 (19.62%) indicated a career preference in Medicine and Surgery as their most preferred career choice. Closely preferred are career preference in Microbiology 46 (17.69%) and Computer Science 42 (16.54%), with career preference in Agricultural Science 11 (4.23%) being the least preferred career choice. Hence, it can be seen that the occupations chosen by students were mainly those belonging to high prestige status category, this may be the result of ignorance concerning the variety of occupations available.

Ho₁: There is no significant difference between career preferences and career aspirations among Biology students in Sabon Gari Local Government Area. Kaduna state.

Table 2: Summary of t-test Results on Career Preferences and Career Aspirations among Biology

Variable	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	df	t-cal	P-value	Decision
Career Preferences and Aspirations	260	18.22	21.02	6	1.66	0.44	Retained

Data analyzed in Table 2 revealed that the probability associated with the calculated value of t (1.66) is 0.44. Since the probability value of 0.44 is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is true, therefore Ho, is retained. This means that, there is no statistical significant difference between career preferences and career aspirations among Biology students in Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna state.

Research Question Two: What are the sources of career information available to Biology students in Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State? The data generated were analyzed and used to draw Table 3.

(Assessment of Career Aspiration on Academic Performance among Secondary School Biology ... Junaidu, #. 1. 2025)

Table 3: Biology Students Sources of Career Information

Sources of Career Information	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Class Teacher	24	09.23
Principal	13	05.00
School Guidance Counsellor	18	06.92
Family Discussion	58	22.31
Peers	48	18.46
Media (Radio/Television)	12	04.62
Social Media (Internet)	40	15.38
Magazines	18	06.92
Career Books	19	07.31
Lectures (Class Lessons)	10	03.85
Total	260	100

In rank order, discussion with family/parent took the highest frequency, scoring 22.3 1% as a source of career information for the students as shown in Table 3 Coming next to family discussion as a source of career information is 'peers' with 18.46%. This is situation is deplorable because it is one of the root causes of unrealistic career decisions among youths. Social media (Internet) with 15.38% and knowledge from lectures/class lessons at 3.85% being the least source of career information for the students.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between career aspirations and academic performance among biology students in Sabon Gari Local Government Area, Kaduna state.

Table 4: Summary of t-test Results on Career Aspirations and Academic Performance in Biology

Variable	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Df	t-cal	P-value	Decision
Career Aspirations and Performance	260	7.60	16.94	5	1.19	0.50	Retained

Data analyzed in Table 4 shows that the probability associated with the calculated value of t (1.19) is 0.50. Since the probability value of 0.50 is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is retained, therefore, there is no statistically significant difference between career aspirations and academic performance among Biology students in Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State.

Discussion of Findings

www.zijstemfugusau.com.ng
des@fugusau.edu.ng

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15674301>

(Assessment of Career Aspiration on Academic Performance among Secondary School Biology ... Junaidu, #. 1. 2025)

From the analysis of responses to the research questions for this study, one can see that career aspiration and preference in Biology is important to secondary school students. They seek out information and advice from a variety of different individuals, and they look for professional guidance and direction to help them with their career planning in the field of Biology. These results coupled with previous research of Anwuzia (2023) have found that adolescents are prepared to make career-related decisions from secondary school, Owusu et al, (2021) found that students who do not have career aspiration and preference from their senior secondary school level very often make wrong career decisions, as it will become important at some point in the near future.

The study noted that, the major sources of career information in Biology available to students were social media and discussion from parents and peers. Parents appear to be in a position to provide career-related information and support. Training parents to assist their adolescent with career-related decision making may help them to understand their child's perspectives and career needs, provide appropriate support and encouragement, and enhance the natural alliance that exists between parent and child. Although peers are not likely to be a source for career related guidance, they have been found to be a source of support during the career planning process (Salim et al., 2023). As part of a more formal career planning process, educating students on how to provide support and encouragement to peers may be indicated. This is in-line with the assertion of Wnong et al., (2021) who reported that students find it easier to get career information from their colleagues, thereby taking career counselling from their peers instead of going to their teachers or guidance counsellors.

Conclusion

As a result of the findings from the study, the study identified that career aspirations in the field of Biology is often influenced by students' career knowledge and academic achievement in Biology as a subject in senior secondary school. The major sources of career information available to Biology students are the information from their fellow colleagues and the mass media. However, the influence of school counsellors and library as sources of career information available to students was not felt.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made.

1. Government and NGO'S should provide the necessary school facilities for science (Biology) students in senior secondary schools, such as libraries, laboratories and so on. This is to enable them develop interest in the area of Sciences (Biology).
2. Career professionals such as teachers and counsellors are advised to attend workshops, seminars that will help broaden their skills and knowledge in the field of Biology and its related disciplines.

References

www.zijstemfugusau.com.ng
des@fugusau.edu.ng

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15674301>

(Assessment of Career Aspiration on Academic Performance among Secondary School Biology ... Junaidu, #. 1. 2025)

- Aileni, M. (2022). Environment sustainability and role of biotechnology. *Innovations in environmental biotechnology*, 21-64.
- Anwuzia, E. (2023). Adolescents' future career preparation and socioemotional competencies: A self-determination theory perspective. *In Self-determination theory and socioemotional learning* (145-166). Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore.
- Brahma, R. (2025). Innovations in teaching and learning for environmental education. *Journal of the American Institute*, 2(2), 210-224.
- DeBoer, G. (2019). *A history of ideas in science education*. Teachers college press.
- Drymiotou, I., Constantinou, C. P., & Avraamidou, L. (2021). Enhancing students' interest in science and understandings of STEM careers: the role of career-based scenarios. *International Journal of Science Education*, 43(5), 717-736.
- Eccles, J. S., & Wigfield, A. (2024). The development, testing, and refinement of Eccles, Wigfield, and colleagues' situated expectancy-value model of achievement performance and choice. *Educational Psychology Review*, 36(2), 51.
- Fowler, S., Roush, R., & Wise, J. (2024). *Concepts of biology*.
- Ghaleb, B. D. S. (2024). The Relationship between Career Selection and Career Satisfaction. *Journal of Business Management and Economic Development*, 2(3), 1045-1056.
- Gutman, L.M., & Akerman, R. (2008). *Determination of aspiration*. London: WBL center for research institute of education.
- Iftikhar, F. (2024). The study of the predictive role of socio economic factors and parental education on students 'career aspiration at the University of Sargodha (Doctoral dissertation, School of Social Sciences & Humanities (S3H), NUST).
- McCartney, M., & Colon, J. (2023). Cornerstone over Capstone: The case for structured career development opportunities early in the undergraduate biology curriculum as a way to influence science and biology identities. *Plos one*, 18(5), e0285176.
- McDonald, K. S., & Hite, L. M. (2023). *Career development: A human resource development perspective*. Routledge.
- Msambwa, M. M., Daniel, K., Lianyu, C., & Fute, A. (2024). A systematic review of the factors affecting girls' participation in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics subjects. *Computer Applications in Engineering Education*, 32(2), e22707.
- Olofin, S. O., Ogunjobi, A. O., Falemu, F. A., & Akinwumi, I. O. (2023). Science Education as a Tool for Achieving Socio-Economic Development of Nigeria. *International Journal of Development and Economic Sustainability*, 11(4), 33-44

www.zijstemfugusau.com.ng
des@fugusau.edu.ng

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15674301>

(Assessment of Career Aspiration on Academic Performance among Secondary School Biology ... Junaidu, #. 1. 2025)

- Owusu, M. K., Owusu, A., Fiorgbor, E. T., & Atakora, J. (2021). Career aspiration of students: The influence of peers, teachers and parents. *Journal of Education, Society and Behavioural Science*, 34(2), 67-79.
- Quinlan, K. M., & Renninger, K. A. (2022). Rethinking employability: how students build on interest in a subject to plan a career. *Higher Education*, 84(4), 863-883.
- Ramly, E.S., Ismail, M., & Juli, J. (2009). Antecedents of career aspirations rural and development professional in Malaysian public organizations. *European Journal for Scientific Research*, 26(1), 66-79.
- Roney, C., & Soicher, H. M. (2022). Work and well-being: collective and individual self-concept, job commitment, citizenship behavior, and autonomy as predictors of overall life satisfaction. *The journal of social psychology*, 162(4), 423-434.
- Salim, R. M. A., Istiasih, M. R., Rumalutur, N. A., & Situmorang, D. D. B. (2023). *The role of career decision self-efficacy as a mediator of peer support on students' career adaptability. Heliyon*, 9(4).
- Shiyo, R. J. (2023). Exploring how advanced-level biology teachers Integrate ict in teaching and learning, A case of one public secondary school in Songwe Region, Tanzania.
- Subasman, I., & Aliyyah, R. R. (2023). The impact of technological transformation on career choices in the STEM sector. *Jurnal Kajian Pendidikan dan Psikologi*, 1(2), 129-142.
- Wong, L. P., Yuen, M., & Chen, G. (2021). Career-related teacher support: A review of roles that teachers play in supporting students' career planning. *Journal of Psychologists and Counsellors in Schools*, 31(1), 130-141.
- Zhang, H., Couch, S., Estabrooks, L., Perry, A., & Kalainoff, M. (2023). Role models' influence on student interest in and awareness of career opportunities in life sciences. *International Journal of Science Education, Part B*, 13(4), 381-399